

ROBUST IMAGE REGISTRATION FOR PERIODIC MATERIALS: APPLICATION TO 3D WOVEN TEXTILES

Aurélie Pillet¹, Kamel Aftisse¹, Jan Neggers¹, Arturo Mendoza³, Julien Schneider² and Stéphane Roux²

¹Univ. Paris-Saclay, CentraleSupélec, ENS Paris-Saclay, CNRS, LMPS, France

²Safran Aircraft Engines, France

³Safran Tech, France

Keywords: Woven composites, Image registration, Large-scale textiles, Textile periodicity

ABSTRACT

This work introduces a robust finite element-based Digital Volume Correlation (FE-DVC) method tailored for the accurate registration of large-scale textile samples. By detecting and correcting shifted periodic regions, the method enables the precise alignment of sample pairs, making it possible to identify subtle textile differences such as those caused by varying weaving parameters. The proposed approach is applied to textile reinforcements used in aircraft engine fan blades, demonstrating robustness and effectiveness in addressing the challenges of complex textile registration tasks.

1 INTRODUCTION

Comparing different measurements (images) can be a challenging task when these are not expressed in the same reference frame. Image registration aims to identify the transformation that best aligns pairs of images. Various techniques exist for this purpose, but FE-based Digital Image Correlation (DIC) in 2D and its 3D counterpart Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) [1] are popular in experimental mechanics for composite materials [2]. DVC, in particular, has been used on woven composites to highlight differences between pairs of samples [3]. In this context, the found transformations inform on any textile difference between samples (e.g., different weaving parameters). These previous studies have shown some potential but have been limited to small samples.

2 METHOD

Registration on larger textiles tends to fail due to the periodicity of the material, which creates local minima that tend to localize into “regions”. Hence, the goal of the present work is to develop a general and robust FE-DVC method for registering large-scale textiles. The largest identified region is heuristically determined to be correct, while the remaining regions are considered shifted. The goal is then to find the displacement (a multiple of the textile period) that corrects the unwanted shift for each misaligned region. The proposed strategy consists in first characterizing all 3D textile periodicities (along warp, weft, and thickness directions) from the image and testing different integer multiples of these shifts which can be ranked according to the induced registration error. If any shift that reduces the registration error is found, it is used to correct the region; otherwise, the found displacement for the region is discarded and a simple extrapolation is used, starting from the largest region, to define a placeholder displacement field. After treating all shifted regions, the new complete transformation is used as initialization for another complete registration process. This process is repeated until no region boundaries remains (i.e., no more shifted regions).

3 RESULTS

The method was applied to multiple large-scale samples of textile reinforcements from aircraft engine fan blades. In all studied cases, no more than three iterations were required to identify the complete correct transformation. As an illustration, the figure below depicts a transversal view of one such textile reinforcement behind an overlay of the longitudinal strain (deformation), computed from the

displacement field obtained from registering two samples. The illustrated field shows highly localized regions in which the warp yarn columns (orthogonal to the image plane) are further apart in the moving (source) image than in the reference (target) one. These results demonstrate the robustness and generality of the proposed method. Indeed, registering different samples serves as a more challenging registration problem than the traditional task encountered in experimental mechanics of registering of the same sample subjected to an external load. Moreover, not only is the proposed method simple to implement it also is non-intrusive, thus it can be used alongside any existing registration method.

Figure 1 Visualization of the horizontal normal strain for a given region of interest

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Roux et al. (2008). Three-dimensional image correlation from X-ray computed tomography of solid foam. *Composites Part A*.
- [2] J. Holmes et al. (2023). Digital image and volume correlation for deformation and damage characterisation of fibre-reinforced composites: A review. *Composite Structures*.
- [3] A. Mendoza et al. (2019). The correlation framework: Bridging the gap between modeling and analysis for 3D woven composites. *Composite Structures*.